

Topic	Guiding question (narrative prompt)	Check - was that mentioned?	Concrete inquiries	Maintenance and control questions
Introduction	Please briefly introduce yourself.	sociodemographic data - age, - gender, pronouns - context [family, occupation]	Do you live alone? <i>[If check questions are not answered specifically, then ask at the end of the interview.]</i>	
Introduction into the topic	To what extent does health play a role in your life?	- personal health history + experiences with doctors + the German health care system - Family context/friends - Pandemic - Work environment/education etc. - Interests	How does that manifest in your everyday life, can you provide an example? [e.g. nutrition etc.]. Do you deal with it a lot? In what sense?	
Information infrastructure: Identify information sources / channels and information needs [Interactive-participative task in the virtual whiteboard Miro]	<i>I am going to share my screen now. To get started, I would like you to take a moment to look at this overview. Think about where or from whom you have received information about health recently.</i> I circle all the terms you mention. <i>[Refer to blank cards for information sources / channels that are not listed at the Miro board.]</i>	Check: Neighbors, news / media, workplace, educational institution, doctor, friend, hospital, communication services, family, scientist, health insurance, pharmacy, social media	If you have questions about your health, where do you get information? Are there perhaps any other terms that are not listed here, but which have also played a role for you?	
Information infrastructure	Do you remember a situation with/in relation to [actor]? Can you tell me more about it? If not: Do you remember the last situation in which health information was shared with you?	How did the situation arise? Did anything seem strange / unusual to you in that context? /	When you think about facilities, people or mediums you use to find out about health. What comes first to your mind?	Can you tell more about it?

		<p>Have you ever had any experiences with false information regarding health? [ask all participants]</p> <p>How did that make you feel?</p> <p>What has the situation done to you / what has the information done to you?</p> <p>How did you deal with it afterwards? Did you share the information with s.o.?</p> <p>What did you do with the information?</p> <p>Has there ever been any problems with that?</p>	<p>Does a specific example come to mind that you can tell me about?</p> <p>Have you ever received e.g. an article where you thought there must be something wrong?</p> <p>What would you say makes an information something you would like to share with others? Why?</p> <p>Do you trust the [actor/source]? (Regarding the accuracy of information, etc.) Why?</p> <p>When you think about your health, who do you (most often) talk to about health topics?</p>	
	<p>Going back to our overview and looking at the different actors/sources, can you tell me whom you trust the most (in terms of information received)?</p>	<p>Check: Go through each actor</p> <p>Was the (health) information credible for you? Why / why not?</p> <p>What would you say made it credible for you?</p> <p>Have you ever received false health information from any of the actors/sources? [ask all participants]</p>	<p>Why?</p> <p>Can you give me an example?</p> <p>Do you remember a situation where your trust was violated in terms of information received? [go through actors/sources]</p> <p>Could you explain where your distrust/trust [actor/source] comes from?</p>	<p>Would you say that influences your behavior?</p>

<p>Health Information behavior Information avoidance / passive information behavior / information anxiety / behavior change</p>	<p>What would you say, what kind of information 'type' are you when it comes to your health?</p> <p>Are you someone who wants a lot of information to feel secure? Or someone who tends to avoid getting too much information, for example, from the internet?</p> <p>Could you briefly explain?</p>		<p>Has anything changed in your behavior over time?</p> <p>What was the trigger for this?</p>	<p>Can you recall a situation where you did not want any health information? If yes, what was it?</p> <p>Can you recall a situation where you actively sought a lot of health information? If yes, what was it?</p>
<p>Scientificity</p>	<p>What do you associate with the word "scientific"?</p> <p>What does it imply for you (something positive / something negative / indifferent)?</p>		<p>For example, when you read a headline of an article that says "New scientific study on XY". What goes through your mind?</p>	<p>To better understand this...</p>
<p>Scientific appearance / participatory part with examples</p>	<p><i>Now we move on to an interactive part, primarily focused on your assessment. I will show you 10 different examples of health information. Please tell me whether the information appears scientific to you or not. For this, we have chosen three colors: pink = scientific, orange = partially scientific, blue = not scientific.</i></p> <p><i>I will assign the colored buttons based on your guidance. Please express everything that comes to your mind as we go through the screenshots.</i></p>		<p>Can you say what appears scientific to you?</p> <p>Can you describe why this appears scientific / not scientific to you?</p> <p>Do you trust this source/information? Why / why not?</p> <p>Is this source / information credible to you? Why? Would you share this information?</p>	<p>If I zoom out once more and show you the overview, would you want to make any changes?</p>
<p>Sociodemographic data [if not mentioned before].</p>	<p>Finally, I would like to ask you a few personal questions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How old are you? - What is your profession? - In which city / district do you live? 		<p>- Gender (ask only if it is not clear from the context)</p>	

Interview conclusion	Is there maybe anything else you have in mind and would like to share? Do you have any open questions that came up during our conversation?			
Closing	Thank you very much for taking the time for the interview. You will receive a thank you for this interview of 30 EUR. We will contact you by mail to ask for your bank account details. If you wish, you are also welcome to participate in another study of our project, where you can also receive an incentive for your participation. If you have any questions, feel free to contact me at any time.		<i>[In case you are interested in participating in another study by the DESIVE² project, I will share the website link in the chat http://www.desive2.org]</i>	

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The study, to which this interview guide belongs, is part of the research project "DESIVE². – Desinformationsverhalten verstehen / Understanding Disinformation Behavior", funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) in Germany as part of the "Agile research – Recognizing and combating digital disinformation campaigns" measure (Grant Agreement No.: 16KIS1529).

Appendix I

Pre-arranged Miro boards for the interactive-participative tasks:

From whom or where do you get health information?

The Miro board contains the following list of sources for health information:

- Health insurance company
- Employer
- Internet
- Doctors
- Neighbors
- Friends
- Hospital
- Communication Apps
e.g. WhatsApp
- Education Center
- Family
- Pharmacy
- News
- Social Media

To the left of the list, there are four sticky notes (green, blue, pink, orange) and a grid of 20 empty circles (5 rows by 4 columns) for participants to place their responses.

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2 What actually looks scientific to me?

Scientific
Party scientific
not scientific

YouTube

Instagram

Twitter

MEIN ARTIKEL

Book

YouTube

REKOMMENDATION

Umschau

Twitter

YouTube